

Reimagining the Russian Self: A Constructivist Approach to Russia's Foreign Policy Narratives

Rus Benliğini Yeniden Düşünmek: Rusya'nın Dış Politika Anlatılarına İnşacı Bir Yaklaşım

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Öz

Bu makale, Sovyetler Birliği'nin dağılması sonrasında içsel kimlik tartışmalarının Rus dış politikasını nasıl derinden şekillendirdiğini incelemektedir. Rusya'nın stratejik davranışını yalnızca materyalist ya da realist yaklaşımlar üzerinden değerlendirmek yerine bu analiz; devlet eylemlerini etkileyen sembolik, düşünsel ve kültürel boyutları ön plana çıkarmaktadır. Rusya'nın geleneksel değerlerin koruyucusu olarak konumlandırılması, özgün bir Avrasya medeniyetinin merkezi gücü olarak tasavvur edilmesi, Batı kaynaklı Rusofobinin hedefi olarak sunulması ve çok kutuplu bir uluslararası sistemin savunucusu olarak tanımlanması... Bu anlatılar, Rus liderliğinin Batı'dan kaynaklanan sistematik dışlanma ve varoluşsal tehdit algısı karşısında tutarlı ve istikrarlı bir benlik anlayışı sağlayarak, hayati ontolojik güvenlik işlevleri görmektedir. Rusya'nın kimliğinin 1990'larda liberal Batıcı eğilimlerden, 2000'lerde medeniyet temelli Avrasyacı bir konuma evrilmesi, dış politika kararlarının yorumlanması ve meşrulaştırılmasında kullanılan bilişsel bir çerçeve işlevi görmüştür. 2022 yılında Rusya'nın Ukrayna'yı işgali, bu kimlik anlatılarının jeopolitik eylemleri yayılcı olmaktan ziyade savunmacı ve varoluşsal olarak sunmak amacıyla nasıl seferber edildiğini açık biçimde ortaya koymaktadır. Son olarak bu çalışma, Rusya'nın güncel dış politikasının, değişen öz algısından ayrı düşünülemediğini ve bu anlatı inşasının Rusya'nın uluslararası düzenle kurduğu ilişkiyi şekillendirmede belirleyici bir rol oynadığını ileri sürmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Rusya, Rus Dış Politikası, Kimlik Siyaseti, Avrasyacılık, Yapısalcılık

Abstract

This article examines how domestic identity contestations have deeply shaped Russian foreign policy since the Soviet Union's dissolution. Rather than viewing Russia's strategic behavior through purely materialist or realist lenses, the analysis foregrounds the symbolic, ideational, and cultural dimensions that influence state actions. Russia as a custodian of traditional values, a central force within a unique Eurasian civilization, a target of Western Russophobia, and a proponent of a multipolar international system... These narratives serve vital ontological security purposes by providing a coherent and stable sense of self amid what Russian leaders perceive as systemic exclusion and existential threat from the West. The evolution of Russia's identity from liberal Westernist aspirations in the 1990s to a civilizational, Eurasianist posture in the 2000s has functioned as a cognitive framework through which foreign policy decisions are interpreted and justified. In 2022, Russia's invasion of Ukraine clearly demonstrated how these identity narratives were mobilized to frame geopolitical actions as defensive and existential rather than expansionist. Finally, this paper contends that Russia's contemporary foreign policy is inseparable from its evolving self-perception and that narrative construction is pivotal in shaping Russia's engagement with the international order.

Keywords: Russia, Russian Foreign Policy, Identity Politics, Eurasianism, Constructivism

1. Introduction

In the post-Soviet era, constructivism provides a valuable analytical framework for understanding the dynamics of Russia's relations with the West, offering practical insights into the interplay between norms and interests. While Russia's normative preferences tend to be articulated through a discourse of material interests, Western narratives are largely grounded in normative and value-based frameworks. Within this embedded context of interest-driven interactions, a constructivist analysis offers a distinct advantage in explaining the underlying mechanisms shaping these divergent approaches (DeBardeleben, 2012).

During the late 2000s and early 2010s, Russia's dominant self-conception became increasingly associated with the notion of the *Russkiy Mir* (Russian World), an imagined community grounded in shared references to the Russian language, culture and a glorified common past. Although this period witnessed a notable intensification of Russia's public diplomacy efforts in Ukraine, such initiatives ultimately failed to transform the psychological climate of Russia-Ukraine relations. The reason was that the identity projected by Russia was fundamentally incompatible with one of Ukraine's primary identity discourses and only partially aligned with another (Feklyunina, 2016). In this regard, even when the concept of "Russophobia" was not explicitly articulated in official discourse, it gradually became a foundational component of Russian foreign policy. For Russia, whose national identity has, to a significant extent, been constructed around the notions of Western threat and opposition, the Russophobia narrative serves not merely as a propaganda instrument, but as a deliberate strategy for defining its relationship with the external world through identity codes rooted in antagonism toward the West. Russia's persistent sense of marginalization within what it perceives as a "unipolar" or "hegemonic" Western order reinforces this narrative, which in turn aligns closely with Russia's long-standing claim, expressed over the past three centuries, that it constitutes a "natural great power" (Tsygankov, 2016).

From a constructivist perspective, the possibility of reversing this posture depends on several conditions: Firstly, the position of international normative authority must be relatively secure; secondly, governing elites generally share existing international norms but question how these norms are operationalized growing domestic support for a particular self-image renders imitative conformity politically costly for the elites; lastly, when elites possess limited material and social resources to engage in competitive confrontation, adopting such a strategy becomes appealing (Narozhna, 2021). In circumstances where competition and cooperation cannot coexist within a shared normative space, states tend to construct their own narratives to legitimize their actions. Russia's anti-Western stance and its emphasis on the Russian World discourse are consistent with this logic. Eventually, by combining constructivist and role-theoretical insights, this study explores how identity narratives not only define Russia's self-perception but also prescribe foreign policy roles within the international system.

Expanding further on this theoretical synthesis, this study intends to explore how the identity narratives of Russia, the Russian World and the Russophobia discourse, have been transformed from mere rhetoric into deeply entrenched institutionalized foreign policy positions that limit Russia's strategic options towards the West. While extensive literature has highlighted the ongoing identity crisis in post-Soviet Russia, a crucial question that remains unanswered is what drives this contradictory identity coding, resulting in the resistance to normative consensus despite material incentives pointing towards the contrary. Therefore, the main research question posed by this article is concerned with the extent to which the convergence of the Russian World and Russophobia narratives produces a rigid foreign policy position that inherently precludes any attempt at aligning normative systems between Russia and the West. To address this problem, the study tests two interrelated sub-

hypotheses: First, that the domestic institutionalization of the Russian World narrative renders any departure from an anti-Western stance politically prohibitive for Russian elites. Second, that the weaponization of the Russophobia discourse functions as a psychological defense mechanism that legitimizes Russia's self-proclaimed "great power" status in response to perceived Western hegemony.

The significance of this study is reflected on both theoretical and empirical levels as a result of combining constructivist and role theoretic approaches which demonstrates how the state identity codes affect the very process of international conflicts instead of simply reflecting them. On an empirical level, this work provides a better evaluation of the modern foreign policy of Russia as well as contributes significantly to the understanding of the psychological barriers making the future cooperation with Russia difficult. Shifting the focus from a purely geopolitically driven materialistic approach to a more psychological one, considering the mental constructs of the Russian elite, this study provides a strong theoretical foundation for analyzing the deadlock in the Euro-Atlantic security structure.

2. Constructing the Constructivism

Constructivism developed during the late 1980s and early 1990s as a direct response to the predictive and explanatory failures of mainstream, rationalist theories, namely neorealism and neoliberalism, in the wake of the sudden and peaceful collapse of the Soviet Union (Katzenstein, 1996). Rationalist frameworks, which treated state preferences and the international structure as fixed and exogenous, were theoretically ill-equipped to account for a systemic transformation driven primarily by domestic ideational shifts, normative changes, and Mikhail Gorbachev's new thinking (Ruggie, 1998). This monumental gap in the literature exposed the limitations of materialist and individualist ontologies. Consequently, scholars like Nicholas Onuf (1989), who coined the term, and subsequently Alexander Wendt, sought to construct an alternative paradigm that could explain how the social world is made and remade through human practice, thereby bridging the epistemological divide between rationalist and post-positivist approaches (Adler, 1997).

The end of the Cold War brought about a rapidly transforming international system, one that challenged traditional notions of state sovereignty and rendered conventional explanatory frameworks inadequate for understanding the complexities of global economic, political, social, and cultural relations (Bozdağlıoğlu, 2023). In response to these transformations, new theoretical perspectives emerged to interpret the evolving nature of international interactions. Among them, constructivism, gaining significant prominence and influence during the 1990s under the intellectual leadership of Alexander Wendt, sought to demonstrate that the international system is not a fixed material reality but a socially constructed one shaped by intersubjective meanings and shared understandings (Wendt, 1999).

Constructivism provides a coherent and comprehensive critique of the fundamental principles of realism with regard to the nature of international relations as material, atomized, and static. According to neorealist perspective, the international system is characterized by structural anarchy, which forces rational and egoistic actors to remain forever trapped in the cycle of the security dilemma, as survival depends solely on material power distribution (Waltz, 1979). Constructivism questions this premise both theoretically and empirically. In terms of theory, the constructivist argument is that anarchy itself has no intrinsic and immutably established logic, as Wendt (1992) puts it, "anarchy is what states make of it." Material power acquires its meaning depending on the intersubjective knowledge held by actors. In practice, while British nuclear arms are not structurally dangerous to the United States, North Korean nuclear capacity poses a significant security threat to it. Therefore, material power has its meaning only when embedded into certain historical context and social relations (Wendt, 1999). Finally, while realists treat interests as exogenous and static, constructivists view interests as endogenous and identity-based (Hopf, 1998).

Any action will either reproduce or transform aspects of the social structure, and the resulting structural outcomes may be intended or unintended. Broadly, social action is both a product and a process. In this context, Bozdağlıoğlu (2011), analyzing the impact of identity on foreign policy formulation and implementation in the case of Türkiye, argues that identity functions as a bridge between environmental structures and state interests. He further highlights the limitations of Wendt's (1992) anarchic framework, noting that it does not predict whether two states will perceive each other as friends or adversaries, recognize each other's sovereignty, maintain dynastic ties, or adopt revisionist or status quo positions; rather, such outcomes are shaped by the level and nature of interactions between the states. However, anarchy does not convey a singular meaning, as multiple perspectives exist regarding its interpretation. The nature of anarchy may vary according to the dominant norms, rules, principles, shared knowledge, and collective expectations that define it (Viotti & Kauppi, 2023).

The constructivist theory encompasses a range of diverse perspectives. One such perspective emphasizes the significance of both normative and material structures, the role of identity in shaping political action, and the mutually constitutive relationship between agents and structures (Reus-Smit, 2005). Despite these variations, all approaches converge on three core assumptions: Social structures are as important as material ones, social structures possess not only a regulative but also a constitutive effect, and agents and structures are mutually constituted (Bozdağlıoğlu, 2023). Besides, one of the core arguments of the theory is that the world we inhabit is socially constructed. In this sense, notions such as norms, ideas, knowledge, and culture possess inherently structural characteristics and play a crucial role in shaping both international relations and the broader international system (Finnemore & Sikkink, 1998).

If actors' identities form the basis of their interests, it becomes essential to distinguish between social and institutional identities. Institutional identity constitutes the actor's individuality and generates four core interests: Physical security, predictability in relations with the world, recognition as an actor by others and economic development (Wendt, 1994). In the context of Russian foreign policy, these institutional imperatives help explain how Russia's self-conception, shaped through narratives like Russophobia and the Russian World, informs both its strategic choices and its interactions with the West. In contrast to the mechanistic nature of the deterministic model, constructivism provides a social ontology where the constitutive connection between agency and structure, both of which refer to states, is highlighted. Unlike the static description of structures' persistence provided by the realists, constructivism offers dynamic models like "the logic of appropriateness" (March & Olsen, 1998), the "life cycle of norms" and "strategic socialization" (Finnemore & Sikkink, 1998). In doing so, constructivism replaces the realist understanding of the "reified" international structure with the idea of a social world where international organizations and global norms have the power to define actors and establish the limits of proper state conduct (Reus-Smit, 2005). The most important explanatory strength of the paradigm in question is its potential to explain how changes in identity can transform historical enmities into a community of cooperative action, or vice versa, how differences in identity codes result in the establishment of conflict institutions. As the theory shows, it is possible to understand that international reality consists of a continuing social process, giving international relations theory the terminology needed to study the ideologically driven aspects of foreign policy.

3. Narratives of “*государство-матрёшка*”¹

Constructivism draws a clear distinction between state identity and interests. While neorealism assumes that both are given and fixed, constructivism contends that identity becomes endogenous to interactions among states. In contrast to the neorealist perspective, states first form their identities through processes of social interaction and subsequently define their interests. From this standpoint, constructivism emphasizes that state interests are not inherently egoistic, as neorealism suggests (Bozdağlıoğlu, 2023). Constructivist scholars emphasize the significance of identity, as it serves as the foundation for shaping a state’s preferences and the behaviors that emerge from them. The processes through which state identities are formed and transformed constitute a core focus within the constructivist research agenda (Hopf, 1998). Moreover, identity offers actors a framework for comprehending their own position within the social world as well as their relationships with other actors (Flockhart, 2024).

According to Wendt, it is necessary to distinguish between corporate and social identities in understanding state identity. Corporate identity refers to the intrinsic, self-organizing characteristics that define the individuality of an actor, underpinning core interests such as physical security, predictability in relations with the world, recognition by other actors, and economic development. In contrast, social identity encompasses the set of meanings an actor attributes to itself as a social entity, taking into account how it is perceived by others in the international system (Wendt, 1994). State identities and interests are not fixed or predetermined but are socially constructed and subject to transformation through multiple levels of interaction, individual, domestic, systemic, and transnational. In an anarchic international system, these identities evolve through ongoing processes of socialization, interpretation, and normative engagement, rendering them a crucial dependent variable in understanding state behavior (Wendt, 1992). Such a framework is essential for analyzing how Russia’s foreign policy narratives have developed in response to identity contestations rather than material imperatives. Russia’s evolving conception of the self, shuttling between Western-oriented liberalism and civilizational exceptionalism, illustrates how discourse and identity co-produce foreign policy choices. By interpreting Russia’s strategic narratives through a constructivist lens, this study highlights how meanings, norms, and identity performances shape Russia’s external conduct, particularly in its relations with the West. Accordingly, Russia’s identity and foreign policy narratives, constructed around its opposition to the West, should be understood not merely through a materialist logic of interests but through ideational processes. On the other hand, Wendt’s (1992) assertion that identities constitute the foundation of interests provides a theoretical basis for understanding how Russia’s Russophobia narrative shapes its foreign policy objectives through a self-conception constructed in opposition to the West.

The above-mentioned theoretical separation of corporate and social identities in constructivism highlights the exact location at which the application of role theory becomes essential. Corporate identity establishes what the fundamental existential necessities of the state are, while social identity is incomplete if it does not include taking on particular international roles. Role theory serves this function in regard to the social identity of the state by explaining how states can cope with the structural strain between "ego expectations," the self-perception of a state about its role within the international system, and "alter expectations," meaning roles assigned to a state by other members of the system (Holsti, 1970; Thies, 2013). Within this framework, roles cannot be seen simply as masks worn by rational actors but as the embodiment of a state's social identity. As soon as there is an imbalance between ego and alter expectations, identity struggle will follow. In other words, the assignment of foreign policy roles plays an important part when it comes to seeking acknowledgment

¹ The concept of layered state structures in Russia is often referred to as *государство-матрёшка* (Matryoshka State)

from the prevailing international order or constructing an alternative narrative to undermine it (Cantir & Kaarbo, 2012).

On the other hand, role theory, which is closely related to the process of identity construction, assumes that states assume specific roles within the international system, which in turn shape their behavior in both domestic and foreign policy arenas (Harnisch et al., 2011). Such roles may include categories like "regional leader," "guarantor of peace," or "anti-Western actor" reflecting normative expectations and perceived obligations regarding appropriate state conduct. While not all foreign policy decisions are purely subjective, objective factors also play a role; however, their influence is more pronounced during the implementation stage rather than in the formation of policy preferences (Ovali & Bozdağlıoğlu, 2012). Within this framework, Russia's Russophobia narrative constitutes an identity construction centered on opposition to the West, and role theory elucidates how this identity aligns with specific foreign policy roles, such as that of a "regional power" or an "anti-European leader."

Between 2000 and 2002, Russia was largely characterized by an image of a "weak state" due to the prominence of terrorism-related concerns. Nonetheless, during the 2006–2008 period, the Kremlin sought to construct a narrative of a "strong Russia" by emphasizing internal consolidation and renewed confidence. Despite these striking shifts in official identity and security discourse, the interconnection between internal and external security persisted, with both domains remaining closely linked through the conceptualization of Russia's state identity. In both the early and later phases of this period, external security priorities, particularly those related to relations with the West and international terrorism played a significant role in shaping domestic threat perceptions under Putin's regime. Toward the later years of Putin's early presidency, this dynamic led to the broadening of the threat image, which came to encompass not only terrorism but also liberal actors and NGOs perceived as aligned with Western influence (Snetkov, 2012).

The process of securitization under Putin's government highlights the fact that another important principle in constructivist role theory is the dynamic nature of foreign policy roles and the ongoing contestation and negotiation in the domestic sphere. The widening scope of Russia's security threat perception, from local terrorism to Western-backed civil society organizations, is consistent with the way critical constructivists define boundary erosion between domestic and systemic levels (Neumann, 2016). Against such backdrop, Russia's move from a "weak state" to a "resurgent great power," following the September 11 attacks and in the lead up to 2008, was more due to discursive shifts rather than changes in capabilities. This explains why through the labeling of liberalism and transnational organizations as a threat to its organizational self-conception, the Russian government could successfully employ the Russophobia discourse to justify a foreign policy role that hinges on the concept of civilizational exceptionalism. As a result, consolidation at the domestic level and confrontation abroad became mutually reinforcing ideational processes with the other being socially constructed by the self (Tsygankov, 2012).

When the concept of sovereignty is taken as the focal point, constructivism offers a broader and more nuanced analytical framework compared to realism. The post-Soviet challenge of constructing a new national identity, the influence of cultural and historical interpretation, Russian notions of a hostile "other" and locally rooted understandings of federalism all contribute valuable insights into the contradictions of Russian foreign policy. The emergence of new postmodern norms, largely shaped under Western dominance and perceived as constraining state sovereignty, appears to remain a key factor underpinning the persistent tensions between Russia and the West (Ziegler, 2012).

The disagreement surrounding the nature and criteria of sovereignty clearly shows the inherent interpretive superiority of constructivist theory when compared to neorealist materialism. While the latter views sovereignty as a stable attribute based on the legal status established as a result of the state's ability to protect its territory, constructivism approaches sovereignty from the perspective of a

socially constructed concept an understanding created and recreated through practice at the international level (Biersteker & Weber, 1996). The clash of interests between post-Soviet Russia and Western countries should be seen in terms of the ontological confrontation over the meaning of sovereignty in a postmodern world. While the Western approach defines sovereignty through the liberal discourse of globalization and places a condition on national legitimacy by requiring universal observance of human rights along with external institutional control, Russia prefers the classical Westphalian doctrine of “absolute sovereignty” which is defined in terms of civilizational self-reliance and non-interference. By focusing on these clashing normative frameworks, constructivism illuminates why the relationship is characterized by structural deadlock. The conflict is not merely a competitive scramble for relative gains or geographical buffer zones, but a deeper, intersubjective struggle over the very rules of recognition that govern the international system.

4. Conclusion

Constructivism highlights the significance of culture, identity, and norms in international relations, aspects often overlooked by rationalist theories. Two key contributions of constructivism to the discipline are particularly noteworthy: first, structures are inherently social, and actors and structures are mutually constitutive; second, state identities and interests are not predetermined but are formed through processes of interaction. While social structures shape state identities and behavior, states can also transform these structures through their practices. Identity constitutes the foundation of interests (Bozdağlıoğlu, 2023).

Russia’s foreign policy since the collapse of the Soviet Union cannot be adequately explained through materialist or realist frameworks alone. Instead, Russia’s strategic behavior is deeply intertwined with domestic identity constructions, which shape both its perceptions of the international environment and the policies it pursues. The evolution of Russia’s self-conception from liberal Westernist orientations in the 1990s to a civilizational, Eurasianist posture in the 2000s illustrates how identity narratives operate as cognitive frameworks that guide foreign policy choices, legitimize actions, and provide ontological security in the face of perceived external threats (Feklyunina, 2016; Tsygankov, 2016). Narratives such as the Russian World and Russophobia not only reflect Russia’s understanding of its historical and civilizational uniqueness but also underpin its positioning as a regional power resisting Western hegemony.

Moreover, applying constructivist and role-theoretical lenses clarifies the mechanisms through which these identity narratives influence state behavior. Institutional and social identities generate core interests including security, recognition, predictability, and economic development which help explain Russia’s policy preferences and its engagement with the West (Wendt, 1992; 1994; Harnisch et al., 2011). Russia’s actions are not merely reactive to material constraints but are actively shaped by ideational processes, norms, and self-perception. In this context, it is reasonable to assume that the implementation of a specific foreign policy requires consensus and negotiation among various groups involved in identity and interest construction, each possessing different role identities. In elite pluralism, a state’s identity and consequently its interests emerge from the contestation among diverse domestic actors seeking to influence the direction of the state (Bozdağlıoğlu, 2011). The narratives of Russophobia and the Russian World are not merely top-down constructs imposed by a single authority; rather, they reflect the interplay and negotiation among different elite factions, bureaucratic institutions, and societal constituencies. Russia’s anti-Western posture and its assertion as a regional power are therefore shaped not only by strategic material considerations but also by the domestic contestation over identity, wherein various actors contribute to the formulation, legitimation, and dissemination of these narratives. This perspective underscores the importance of considering the internal dynamics of identity construction when analyzing Russian foreign policy behavior, particularly in its engagement with the West and its responses to perceived threats.

The Russophobia narrative forms an integral component of Russia's quest for ontological security: Russian leaders and the public resist Western characterizations of Russia as a "minor power" or a "compliant actor," framing such perceptions through the lens of a pervasive anti-Russian sentiment. Aggressive policy actions, such as the 2022 military intervention in Ukraine, cannot be fully explained by materialist logic alone; rather, they acquire meaning within identity-driven and narrative-based frameworks. Constructivist theory underscores this dynamic by emphasizing that state interests are not fixed givens but emerge from identities and interactions. This perspective aligns with Russia's strategic utilization of narratives, which not only serve to legitimize its actions but also reinforce a victim identity and facilitate the construction of alternative norms and modes of engagement with the West.

The empirical path of post-Soviet Russian foreign policy confirms the central theoretical assertion of this paper. The interrelation between the narratives of the Russian World and Russophobia has served to lock Russia into a rigidly hostile stance, which cannot be easily reversed. Such ideational constructs have become more than mere instruments of rhetoric, as they are now thoroughly entrenched on a domestic level and any attempt by Moscow to adopt a cooperative approach towards the West would be politically infeasible for the Kremlin establishment. The deployment of Russophobia narrative operates as a crucial psychological safeguard, recasting international ostracism and economic penalties not as signs of tactical failure but evidence of the correctness of Russia's claims of being a natural great power, victimized by systemic discrimination. Hence, the Kremlin finds itself with limited opportunities in light of the identity framework it had created for itself, demonstrating the ways in which a socially constructed reality may establish a rigid and unyielding geopolitical path dependence, resistant to rationalist calculations of costs and benefits. The structural deadlock in Euro-Atlantic relations, evident in the 2022 invasion of Ukraine, stems not only from fluctuations in material power or geography-related concerns but also an existential contestation regarding the core principles of international recognition. As long as Russia's corporate identity relies on the hostile other for legitimacy, while the social identity rejects liberal boundaries of post-war sovereignty, diplomatic solutions would prove to be inadequate.

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